

Alkali Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with Biuret*

A. K. BANERJEE, T. K. SINHA and S. K. ROY

Chemistry Department, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 21 July 1978, revised 15 November 1978, accepted 12 March 1979

Adducts of alkali metal salts of some organic acids with biuret of the general formula $ML \cdot Biuret$ (where $M = Li, Na \text{ \& } K$ and $L = \text{organic acids}$) have been synthesised and their structures investigated with particular regard to the coordination sites in biuret. These were isolated from ethanol or acetone solutions and are expected to contain biuret coordinated to the metal ion in a cationic species. Infrared results suggest that in these metal complexes, the biuret is coordinated as a bidentate ligand through two oxygen atoms.

The present work also shows that hydrogen bonding is not necessary for formation of adducts between a chelating ligand and the alkali metal salt of a chelate anion.

A number of stable adducts of alkali metal salts of organic acids with biuret of the general formula $ML \cdot Biuret$ (where $M = Li, Na \text{ \& } K$ and $L = \text{organic acids}$) have been synthesised. Analytical data showed that one molecule of lithium, sodium and potassium salts of organic acids combined with one molecule of biuret, suggesting a coordination number four for the metal atom. Using as 'standards' compounds whose structures have been determined by X-ray analysis, it has been possible to confirm, by infrared measurements, the mode of coordination of biuret in other metal complexes.

Experimental

The synthetic method was almost the same for all the systems, apart from the reaction medium which was either absolute ethanol or acetone, as indicated in Table 1. Acetone was used when no adduct could be isolated from absolute ethanol. The general method of preparation was to take the alkali metal salts of the organic acids and biuret, in equimolar ratio, (except in the cases of 2, 4DNP, 2, 6DNP and SalH) in ethanol/acetone and then to reflux on a hot plate with magnetic stirrer for about one hour. On cooling the solution, crystals were obtained. The compounds were filtered, washed, with the solvent and dried at 80° . In case of Li_2 , 4DNP.Bt and Li_2 , 6DNP.Bt, crystals were obtained only when the solution was left in a refrigerator overnight, in an air-tight container.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are stable in dry air, but in the case of 8-hydroxyquinoline complexes, they

decompose readily on exposure to air, to a dark-brown solid. It is presumably hydrolysed by the moisture of the atmosphere. These complexes were kept in a desiccator over solid anhydrous calcium chloride or sodium hydroxide pellets. The complexes are slightly soluble in most polar solvents but are insoluble in non-polar solvents. The colour, and the melting ($m^\circ C$) or the transition ($t^\circ C$) or decomposition ($d^\circ C$) temperatures and analysis of the complexes are given in Table 1.

McLellan^{1,2} points out that in a carbonyl stretching region, $1750 - 1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ the spectrum consists of one strong broad band centred at approximately $1680 - 90 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a very much weaker band at approximately 1620 cm^{-1} . Similar frequency shifts of carbonyl stretching modes have been reported in some mono- and di-amide complexes^{3,4} and also in urea complexes⁵.

The complexes formed between biuret and several acid salts of alkali metals have the general formula $ML \cdot Biuret$; these were isolated from ethanol or acetone solutions and are expected to contain biuret coordinated to the metal ion in a cationic species.

Since in transition metal complexes in neutral solution, the biuret is coordinated as a bidentate ligand through two oxygen atoms, it is suggested, because of the similarity of the infrared spectra of all the alkali metal biuret complexes to that of the transition metal biuret complexes, that the mode of coordination of biuret is the same in all of them.

* The paper published in the Proceedings of the XVI International Conference on Co-ordination Chemistry, Dublin, 1974, R3, 3pp.

TABLE 1—MELTING (m), TRANSFORMATION (t), OR DECOMPOSITION (d) POINTS AND CHEMICAL ANALYSES

Compound	Colour	Temperature (°C)	Found(%)				Calculated (%)			
			C	H	N	Metal	C	H	N	Metal
Li1N2N.Bt ^a	Green	210-15d	50.40	4.30	20.20	—	51.06	3.90	19.85	—
Na1N2N.Bt ^b	Green	240-45d	47.90	4.00	19.00	7.82	48.32	3.69	18.79	7.71
K1N2N.Bt ^b	Light Green	160-65d	46.00	3.50	17.90	12.40	45.85	3.50	17.83	12.42
LiONP.Bt ^a	Orange Yellow	150-60d	39.30	3.50	21.95	—	38.71	3.63	22.58	—
NaONP.Bt ^b	Red	165t	36.46	4.00	21.70	8.64	36.36	3.41	21.21	8.71
KONP.Bt ^b	Orange	135-40m	34.60	3.61	19.65	13.88	34.28	3.21	20.00	13.93
Li2,4DNP.Bt ^a	Cream	165m	32.52	2.80	23.68	—	32.76	2.73	23.89	—
Na2,4DNP.Bt ^a	Red	200d	30.69	2.90	22.45	7.51	31.07	2.59	22.65	7.44
K2,4DNP.Bt ^a	Red	175-80m	28.95	3.20	21.37	11.86	29.54	2.46	21.54	12.00
Li2,6DNP.Bt ^a	Light Yellow	175-79m	32.36	2.94	23.48	—	32.76	2.73	23.89	—
Na2,6DNP.Bt ^a	Red	210-15d	30.80	2.81	22.10	7.44	31.07	2.59	22.65	7.44
K2,6DNP.Bt ^a	Red	180-85d	29.10	2.80	20.92	11.88	29.54	2.46	21.54	12.00
Li8HQ.Bt ^b	Pale Yellow	160d	52.10	4.50	22.40	—	51.97	4.33	22.05	—
Na8HQ.Bt ^b	Dirty White	175-80d	49.10	3.91	20.52	8.49	48.89	4.10	20.74	8.52
K8HQ.Bt ^b	Dirty White	180-85d	45.81	4.10	19.30	13.54	46.15	3.85	19.58	13.64
NaAnth.Bt ^b	Grey	140-45t/d	40.32	4.93	20.81	8.81	40.75	5.28	21.13	8.68
KAnth.Bt ^b	Light Brown	155-60t/d	38.15	4.49	20.08	13.75	38.43	4.98	19.93	13.88
NaGly.Bt ^b	Pale Yellow	175-80m̄d	23.85	4.20	28.20	11.20	24.00	4.50	28.00	11.50
NaONBA.Bt ^b	Dirty White	90-95m	36.55	3.40	19.05	7.88	36.98	3.08	19.18	7.88
KONBA.Bt ^b	White	155-60m	34.80	3.10	18.31	12.48	35.07	2.92	18.18	12.66
NaSalA.Bt ^b	White	180t, 270d	40.78	4.11	15.82	8.55	41.06	3.80	15.96	8.75
KSalA.Bt ^b	White	180-90m̄d	38.45	3.80	15.21	14.00	38.71	3.68	15.05	13.97
LiPicA.Bt ^b	White	235t, 300m̄d	40.91	4.20	23.95	—	41.37	3.88	24.13	—
NaPicA.Bt ^b	White	170-80m	38.32	4.01	22.05	9.40	38.71	3.63	22.58	9.27
KPicA.Bt ^b	White	150t, 280d	35.98	3.93	20.95	14.91	36.36	3.41	21.21	14.77
LiSalH.Bt ^a	White	175-80m	46.11	4.50	17.79	—	46.75	4.33	18.18	—
NaSalH.Bt ^b	Dirty White	192d partly 245d completely	43.39	4.50	17.20	9.30	43.72	4.05	17.00	9.31
NaAsp.Bt ^b	White	210t, 260-80d	40.41	4.41	14.04	7.77	40.95	4.10	14.33	7.85
KAsp.Bt ^b	White	142-46m	38.52	4.20	13.11	12.40	38.83	3.88	13.59	12.62

a=Preparation of the complex in acetone; b=Preparation of the complex in ethanol. Bt=Biuret; 1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol; ONP=o-nitrophenol; 2,4DNP=2,4-dinitrophenol; 2,6-DNP=2,6-dinitrophenol; 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline; Anth=anthranilic acid; Gly=glycine; ONBA=o-nitrobenzoic acid; SalA=Salicylic acid; PicA=Picolinic acid; SalH=Salicylaldehyde; and Asp=Aspirin.

In the carbonyl stretching region 1750–1550 cm^{-1} , the spectra consist of either a band near 1710 cm^{-1} and the other at 1665 cm^{-1} or a strong band centred at approximately 1685 cm^{-1} , with a shoulder at the higher frequency region (Table. 2). It is

suggested that this broad absorption band at 1680 cm^{-1} or 1710 cm^{-1} arises from the symmetric carbonyl stretching mode lowered from 1720 cm^{-1} in biuret. A shift to lower frequency of the carbonyl stretching mode would be expected to occur on coordination through the oxygen atom of the amide group. The C–N stretching band at 1440 cm^{-1} in biuret, is obscured in the spectra of the complexes due to other modes of vibrations of the acid salts.

 TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (cm^{-1})

Biuret	3400	3300	3180	1720	1690
Li1N2N.Bt	3400	3300	3180	1712	1670
Na1N2N.Bt	3400	3300	3180	1705	1680
K1N2N.Bt	3400	3340	3200	1708	1680
LiONP.Bt	3450	3400	3190	1708	1670
NaONP.Bt	3410	3350	3200	1705 ^{sh}	1630
NaONBA.Bt	3400	3320	3180	1705	1670
KONBA.Bt	3400	3300	3185	1710	1670
NaAnth.Bt	3450	3400	3180	1705	1685
KAnth.Bt	3450	3390	3185	1720	1675
NaGly.Bt	3450	3420	3320	3200 ^{br}	1700 ^{sh}
NaSalA.Bt	3400	3300	3190	1708	1665
KSalA.Bt	3420	3380	3190	1700	1680
LiPicA.Bt	3410	3350	3200	1695	1670
NaPicA.Bt	3400 ^{br}	3300	3180	1705 ^{sh}	1690
KPicA.Bt	3400	3300	3180	1705	1675
LiSalH.Bt	3400	3300 ^{br}	3200 ^{br}	1710	1670
NaSalH.Bt	3410	3300 ^{br}	3200 ^{br}	1710	1670
NaAsp.Bt	3420	3320	3200 ^{br}	1710 ^{sh}	1670
KAsp.Bt	3420	3310 ^{br}	3200 ^{br}	1710	1680

sh=shoulder; br=broad.

The N–H stretching vibrations at 3400 and 3300 cm^{-1} in biuret, are either same or lower (Table 2) than in the alkali metal salt—biuret complexes. Thus it appears that the hydrogen bonding present in biuret is reduced slightly on coordination to the alkali metal complexes. The 3180 cm^{-1} band due to —NH— in biuret and the alkali metal complexes remain unaffected. The coordination through two nitrogen atoms of NH_2 , would have resulted in a shift of the N–H stretching vibration of biuret (3400 and 3300 cm^{-1}) to lower frequency; at the same time there would have been no change in the C=O frequency of the biuret.

Our present work also shows that no hydrogen bonding is needed for the formation of adducts

between a chelating ligand and the alkali metal salt of a chelate anion, similar to the adducts of 1, 10-phenanthroline with alkali metal salts^{6,7}. It may be that hydrogen bonding is one of the structure forming features of the ML_nHL and ML_nHL' adducts.

References

1. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, p. 221.
2. A. W. McLELLAN and G. A. MELSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (L)*, 1967, 137.
3. C. S. KRAIHAZEL and S. C. GRENDA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1037.
4. W. E. BULL, S. K. MADAN and J. E. WILLIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 303.
5. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1963, Ed. 2, p. 184.
6. A. K. BANERJEE, A. J. LAYTON, R. S. NYHOLM and MARY R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 1894.
7. A. K. BANERJEE, DEARM PRAKASHI, P. KEJARIWAL and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 691.